

Multifunctionality in Polymer Networks by Dynamic of Coordination Bonds

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The need for multifunctional materials is driven by emerging technologies and innovations, such as in the field of soft robotics and tactile or haptic systems, where minimizing the number of operational components is not only desirable, but can also be essential for realizing such devices. This study report on designing a multifunctional soft polymer material that can address a number of operating requirements such as solvent resistance, reshaping ability, self-healing capability, fluorescence stimuli-responsivity, and anisotropic structural functions. The numerous functional abilities are associated to rhodium(I)–phosphine coordination bonds, which in a polymer network act with their dynamic and non-covalently bonded nature as multifunctional crosslinks. Reversible aggregation of coordination bonds leads to changes in fluorescence emission intensity that responds to chemical or mechanical stimuli. The fast dynamics and diffusion of rhodium–phosphine ions across and through contacting areas of the material provide for reshaping and self-healing abilities that can be further exploited for assembly of multiple pieces into complex forms, all without any loss to material-sensing capabilities.

outcome is a variety of polymeric materials possessing their own set of functions, which are designed by deriving required properties and processes. An example of such systems is conjugated polymers, which exhibit stimuli-responsive fluorescence.^[5–10] This has been recognized as an interesting stimuli-responsive feature with large application potential, especially for creating emissive sensors, indicators, fluorescent probes, or optical detectors.^[4,11]

Molecular design and consideration of dynamics in materials can enable the creation and implementation of multifunctionality in polymeric materials.^[1,12–17] For instance, polymer networks containing covalent netpoints (thermosets) exhibit excellent solvent resistance and mechanical durability, which makes them an attractive candidate material for many demanding applications such as chemical resistant sensors, optical indicators, and

coatings.^[12–15,18,19] In contrast, an attractive and valuable function for non-covalently crosslinked polymers is their capability of shape forming and molding without impairment of mechanical properties.^[1,12–14] The resilience of covalently bonded structure and pliability of non-covalently crosslinked polymers can be combined by designing polymer networks with reversible interactions (e.g., host–guest interaction or dynamic covalent bonds), providing the system with self-healing, contact assembly capabilities or shape-memory capabilities.^[12,13,19–22]

Here we aim at a material exhibiting a range of physical functions in form of chemically and mechanically induced fluorescence emission (FE) intensity changes, shape forming, self-healing capability, and modular fabrication by contact assembly. Our concept for such a multifunctional material is a rhodium–phosphine coordination polymer network (Rh-PCPN) (Figure 1a). The material is composed of linear poly[(*n*-BA)-*co*-DPPST] chains (Figure 1b) that are complexed with [RhCl(COD)]₂ (diphenylphosphinostyrene) dimers to produce a polymer system in which the rhodium–phosphine coordination bonds (Rh-PCBs) act as crosslinkers. Owing to the strong crosslinking nature of Rh-PCBs, this material is expected to withstand high degree of swelling and so is chemically resistant when exposed to high solvent concentrations.

Rh-PCPN's functions are presented in Figure 1c, where the material's functions are associated with the components from which they originate, as well as with required stimuli needed to trigger the listed functions. Here, functions originate predominantly from the coordination bonds. Apart from acting as

1. Introduction

Technological innovations and requirements of modern applications have driven research towards active materials, capable of performing functions in specific system environments.^[1–4] The

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Figure 1. a) Structural schematic of the Rh-PCPN material depicts the material's polymer network, which is interconnected together by rhodium–phosphine crosslinks comprising of aggregated Rh-PCBs. Rh-PCBs can migrate across the material by ligand exchange reactions, providing also for the diffusivity of polymer chains. b) Chemical structure of the polymer chain. c) Diagram of functions maps all functions of the Rh-PCPN material down to their molecular counterpart, i.e., Rh-PCBs (blue area) and polymer network (orange area). Colored circles represent external stimuli under which the material functions are activated or realized. These are the mechanical stimulus in the form of compression and strain (blue circle), the chemical stimulus, which encompasses exposure to organic solvents (green circle), and a change in temperature (red circle), i.e., heating and cooling to promote or demote ligand exchange rate and thus pliability and self-healing capabilities of the material.

crosslinks, the phosphine ligands coordinated around rhodium ions are capable of FE. Rh-PCBs tend to aggregate; therefore, their dissociation and recombination leads to aggregation-induced emission. It will be shown that changes in FE intensity through Rh-PCB dissociation can be triggered chemically by exposing the material to organic solvents, as well as mechanically via stretching of the polymer network by application of external stress. Conjugated polymers and elastomers with FE capabilities are candidate materials to employ as soft sensor devices, which can be susceptible to changes in temperature,^[7,9] pH,^[10] solvents,^[9,10] and other stimuli.^[5,6,8,23] The Rh-PCPNs can, thus, be implemented as chemically and mechanically responsive elastic sensors. The ligand exchange rate and overall polymer chain mobility is increased with temperature, which also helps to speed up recombination of Rh-PCBs. The specimen, therefore, can be reshaped—once the material is heated and deformed, the Rh-PCBs quickly reconfigure into a new crosslinking topology and the material's new shape is preserved. Moreover, the polymer network retains the instilled orientation after the shape-forming process, which introduces anisotropical mechanical properties to the system. Polymer chains and Rh-PCBs are also capable of collectively diffusing through the contact area, providing for self-healing capabilities and contact assembly. Hence, new complex geometries can be realized that cannot be achieved by conventional polymer processing and molding. Complex geometries and shape adaptability are

desired especially in the ever more developing and prevailing field of soft robotics.^[24,25]

2. Results and Discussion

2.1. FE Properties of Rh-PCPN

Our material's emission properties are based on the aggregation-induced emission (AIE) phenomena, where FE intensity depends on the thermal motion degree of the light emitting molecules, i.e., more restrictive motion results in higher intensity.^[26–29] The aggregation of rhodium–phosphine complexes into Rh-PCB clusters enhances the FE intensity, whereas the intensity is decreased when the coordination points are dissociated either chemically or mechanically.

For the purpose of this study, a series of poly[(*n*-BA)-co-DPPST] samples with varied molar concentrations of diphenylphosphinostyrene (DPPST) were prepared. The sample naming is as follows: P-(*x*) for noncomplexed and Rh-PCPN-(*x*) for rhodium–phosphine-complexed systems. *x* denotes the DPPST molar concentration content, with the typical content feed of 4, 7, and 11 mol% (Tables S1 and S2 and Figure S1, Supporting Information). Rhodium/phosphorous molar stoichiometry was always kept at 1:4; therefore, each rhodium ion was expected to coordinate three to four phosphine ligands. A more

Figure 2. a) UV-vis spectra (dotted lines) show no absorption peak for P-(7) specimen (blue) in contrast to a newly formed peak at 390 nm seen for the rhodium-complexed system (Rh-PCPN-(7), orange). The presence of Rh-PCBs yields a strong intensity emission peak at 683 nm, as indicated by solid-state FE spectroscopy (solid lines). b) SAXS measurements show an appearance of a diffraction peak for Rh-PCPN-(7) (solid line) sample at $s = 0.0316$ nm⁻¹, which does not change with temperature (colored solid lines). No such peak is present for the noncomplexed P-(7) (dashed line in b).

detailed description of the synthesis is provided in the Experimental Section.

Complexed Rh-PCPN systems exhibit an absorption peak at 390 nm (Figure 2a—for Rh-PCPN-(7) specifically), while no such peak is present for the noncomplexed P-(7) sample. This absorption peak indicates a successful coordination reaction assigned to the metal ligand charge transition of Rh-PCBs.^[30,31] When under irradiation with a $\lambda = 400$ nm excitation beam, the introduced rhodium complexes emit a high intensity peak at 683 nm. Small-angle X-ray scattering (SAXS) experiments (Figure 2b) provided evidence of Rh-PCBs aggregation, with an average distance between rhodium–phosphine complexes of 31.5 ± 0.2 nm for Rh-PCPN-(7) samples. These are thought to occur by phase segregation from the *Pn*-BA backbone phase due to each component's immiscibility. Apart from facilitating the system with FE, the Rh-PCB aggregates provide additional stability to the system by acting as non-covalent crosslinkers. Furthermore, they remain utterly unaffected when the temperature was increased (Figure 2b). The formed phase-segregated morphology remains stable even when heated to 100 °C. This is later exploited as means of retaining FE capabilities even after reshaping the material into new geometries.

2.2. Mechanical and Solvent-Responsive AIE

Rhodium–phosphine complexes are shown to possess AIE capabilities and display changes in FE intensity based on the degree of their aggregation in organic solvent mixtures (Figure S2, Supporting Information). In Rh-PCPNs, such changes in FE intensity can be generated by dissociation of Rh-PCB aggregates through either mechanical manipulation or exposing the material to organic solvents.

When the Rh-PCPN specimen is deformed, the FE intensity decreased as the stress was increased (Figure S3, Supporting Information). A remark should be put here that this is not associated particularly to Rh-PCBs dissociation, as concentration changes caused by stretching and spreading of Rh-PCBs outside the observation area contribute as well. On the other hand, FE intensity shows no dependency on the thickness of our samples (Figure S4, Supporting Information). We can assume that only the surface Rh-PCBs are irradiated and contributing to the

detected emission. Even if the deviations in FE intensity are not related only to Rh-PCB aggregate dissociation, the notion of mechanical manipulation of FE intensity nevertheless paves the way towards utilization of Rh-PCPN material for deformation monitoring.

Beside mechanical responsivity, the Rh-PCPN material is also capable of chemically induced FE changes. Exposure to organic solvents promotes higher rhodium-ion mobility while also lessening the network's restrictive impact through swelling of the material. This results in the breakdown of the Rh-PCB aggregates (Figure 3a). Such swelling of the system, however, can have a detrimental effect on the material. A strong enough crosslinking is, therefore, required to retain structural stability when a higher degree of swelling is involved, as well as to allow the system to return to its pre-swollen state without the loss in function.

The general deformability of the Rh-PCPN-(7) was investigated by dynamic mechanical thermal analysis (DMTA) (Figures 4–7). The Rh-PCPN could not be characterized by DMTA below -20 °C because of its brittle nature. When the temperature was raised from -20 to 80 °C, the storage modulus (E') decreased until E' reached a rubbery plateau at 80 °C. The decrease of E' with raising temperature further confirmed the preferable deformation of the sample at elevated temperature.

When Rh-PCPN samples were exposed to various organic solvents (Figure 3b), both Rh-PCPN-(7) and Rh-PCPN-(11) were proven insoluble even when immersed at higher temperatures (50 and 70 °C) and for longer times (96 h), while the Rh-PCPN-(4) sample dissolved in *N,N*-dimethylformamide (DMF). SAXS investigation of a swollen Rh-PCPN-(7) (Figure 3c) shows no existence of Rh-PCBs aggregates and so the material's solvent resistance is attributed to individual Rh-PCBs. The existence of a sufficient number of Rh-PCBs is, therefore, critical to achieve a strong enough crosslinking for solvent resistivity. A low concentration of Rh-PCBs was shown to result in their transformation from inter- to intramolecular coordination crosslinks when subjected to swelling^[32] (Figure S6, Supporting Information), thus making the Rh-PCPN network facile to dissolve.

Polymer materials with AIE capabilities can be difficult to handle when swollen and are as such prone to break down when subjected to larger mechanical stresses. Their

Figure 3. Rh-PCPN samples were subjected to a number of solvents that provided a high solubility for their noncomplexed P-(*x*) counterpart. The solvents used were CHCl₃, toluene, THF, and DMF. a) Solvent exposure leads to swelling of the system and dissociation of Rh-PCB clusters. Individual Rh-PCBs can provide for strong enough crosslinking to prevent dissolution of polymer chains. Graph (b) shows the degree of swelling (blue circles) and crosslink densities (red/orange circles) for the Rh-PCPN-(7) sample. c) SAXS experiments of a swollen Rh-PCPN-(7) specimen shows no diffraction peaks, signifying a complete dissociation of Rh-PCBs aggregates in the swollen state.

Figure 4. a) Dissociation and dispersion of Rh-CPBs can be achieved either by solvent vapor treatment or by mechanical rubbing of the Rh-PCPN surface. b,c) UV-vis experiments performed on a Rh-PCPN-(7) specimen show a decrease in peak intensity at $\lambda = 680$ nm for both treatments. Spectral peaks return to its initial value after CHCl₃ is evaporated (brown to gray line in b), as well as after relaxation of the mechanically agitation polymer network (blue to gray line in c).

Figure 5. a) High elasticity of noncomplexed P-7) material (blue line) apparent in tensile test, while Rh-complexed Rh-PCPN-7) (orange line) is stiffer, followed by a softer regime with increasing strain. b) Several creep tests were performed on an Rh-PCPN-7) sample, showing a time-dependent evolution of strain at different applied loads (black solid and dashed line) and at different temperatures (red and orange solid lines).

implementation as sensors is therefore limited to low-stress environments. Rh-PCPNs exhibit a relatively high Young's modulus (in the range of several MPa) in their non-swollen state, facilitating practical handling and improving mechanical durability. It is then imperative for the Rh-PCPN material to be able to detect small traces of organic solvent before any major swelling occurs that could prove detrimental to its structure and performance. The same applies for mechanical sensing; large stresses can induce plastic deformation of the specimen that can in turn make it inoperative during specific tasks.

Given that the emission of our fluorescent material derives from the surface and that volume change of Rh-PCPN during stimuli is undesirable, we have resolved to organic solvent vapor and rubbing forces as chemical and mechanical stimulus (Figure 4) to check the material's sensitivity.

Vapor of chloroform (CHCl_3) was used as chemical stimulus to induce dispersion of Rh-PCBs on the Rh-PCPN-7) specimen's surface. The solvent vapor treatment was performed by exposing the sample to vapors 5 cm above the CHCl_3 liquid-air interface for $t = 30$ s. UV-vis spectra were measured before and after this treatment. The change in FE intensity after solvent

Figure 6. a) Schematic illustration depicting the shape-forming process that can be used to produce b) intricately shaped specimens, including a fusilli-shaped, wave-shaped, and spring-shaped sample (top to bottom). c) Effect of temperature on the shape-forming process was determined with stress-relaxation measurements. It is seen that almost no internal strain remains for $T = 50$ °C and $T = 80$ °C, indicating a good shape fixation. d) 2D-SAXS experiments were performed on an Rh-PCPN-7) sample before and after the shape-forming process. Original sample displays a diffraction peak at $s = 0.0316 \text{ nm}^{-1}$ (blue solid line), while after reshaping, the peaks are shifted, resulting in peak positions at $s = 0.0295 \text{ nm}^{-1}$ in parallel (red solid line) and $s = 0.0340 \text{ nm}^{-1}$ in perpendicular (red dashed line) direction against the reshaping strain.

Figure 7. a) Rhodium-ion diffusion experiment is shown in the scheme. a1) Two covalently bonded specimens of noncomplexed cc-P sample and rhodium-ion-treated cc-Rh-PCPN were compressed together with a2) 5% compressive strain at controlled temperatures of 4, 20, 50, 80, and 100 °C for 6 h. a3) Afterwards, the treated cc-P layer was separated from the cc-Rh-PCPN and b) examined with UV-vis. Results show higher absorbance of treated cc-P (full lines) when compared to nontreated cc-P (dashed line). The inner graph displays quantification of rhodium-ion concentrations derived from the 410 nm mark using a standard curve. A small peak can be observed at 350 nm, which is linked to experimental artifacts (see Figure S12, Supporting Information).

exposure is significant—a decrease of 40% of the initial FE peak after exposure was detected (Figure 4b). Overlapping UV-vis curves of vapor-treated and untreated Rh-PCPN-(7) proves that the sample volume does not change (Figure S7, Supporting Information) and the intensity of the FE peak returns to its initial value after the solvent has evaporated (Figure 4b). Mechanical treatment was realized by applying mechanical friction to an Rh-PCPN-(7) surface using a rheometer plate. The surface was agitated for 10 min with 10 kPa shear stress at a frequency of 5 Hz (Figure 4c). Results show a reversible and substantial decrease in FE intensity (47%), with no volume change of the specimen as indicated by UV-vis examination (Figure S8, Supporting Information). The treatment of the surface area is sufficient to trigger a noticeable AIE response. Demonstrated sensitivity to solvent vapors gives the material potential to be utilized as vapor detection system, while the solvent resistivity and mechanical durability means that it has the capability of performing in more demanding environments. Even if sensing capabilities are diminished by exposure to larger deformations or swelling, the restructural nature of Rh-PCBs leads to a complete renewal of the material's function once the material recovers to its initial state.

2.3. Structural Function

The primary polymer backbone, poly(*n*-butylacrylate) (P*n*-BA), comprising the Rh-PCPN network has a low glass transition

temperature (T_g) of -44 °C (Figure S9 and Table S3, Supporting Information), is chemically inert, and exhibits high elasticity with the elongation at break of $\epsilon_b \approx 650\%$ at 25 °C (Figure 5a). As discussed before, addition of rhodium ions forms rhodium-phosphine complexes, which among other functionalities act as non-covalent crosslinkers. The addition of the rhodium ions does only cause a very slight increase of T_g , which might be explained by an already phase segregated structure of poly[(*n*-BA)-*co*-DPPST], in which the addition of the rhodium coordination sites would have a lower impact on the reduction of the free volume. The formation of such coordination sites dictates and greatly enhances the material's mechanical properties.^[33,34] In case of Rh-PCPNs, the Young's modulus is increased by an order of magnitude from below 0.6 MPa to above 16.5 MPa (Table S3, Supporting Information). The tensile test performed on Rh-PCPN-(7) (Figure 5a) displays an initial elastic response for loads below 1.2 MPa, which evolves into plastic deformation with increased stress until the sample ruptures at $\epsilon_b \approx 285\%$ strain. The initial mechanical stiffness is ascribed to the disruption and extrication of the polymer network, upon which Rh-PCB aggregates dissociate by increased mechanical stress. After removal of load, Rh-PCBs re-aggregate into a new configuration and some of the deformation is preserved. Creep tests were performed to measure the amount of remaining strain on Rh-PCPN-(7) samples (Figure 5b). These experiments were performed by mechanically loading the sample for $t = 60$ min, after which the load was removed and the sample was left to relax, while the strain was constantly recorded. Different loads

and temperatures were used at each test. Results (Figure 5b) show only negligible residual strain of <1% at room temperature and small loads ($\sigma = 0.1$ MPa), but a clear plastic deformation is observed when the sample is subjected to higher loads of $\sigma = 0.4$ MPa, where 13% of the initially applied 39% strain is retained (Figure 5b, black dashed line). Increased temperature clearly facilitates breakdown of Rh-PCBs, observing 7% of remaining strain at $T = 50$ °C with $\sigma = 0.1$ MPa load. This is especially seen by the large deformation observed at 80 °C, preserving 19% of strain from the applied 41% (Figure 5b, orange line). The high amount of remnant strain hints at faster ligand exchange reactions, which are promoted when temperature is increased. This provides for easier Rh-PCBs dissociation and fast subsequent rearrangement.

2.4. Shape Forming

Increased plasticity of the material at higher temperatures can be exploited for reshaping the material, but the new geometry cannot be entirely preserved as was shown by creep experiments. We attribute this to the residual internal stresses that are high enough to dissociate the temperature-weakened Rh-PCB aggregates after the applied load is removed. For efficient shape preservation, the material should be cooled down after deformation and the applied mechanical field should not be removed during the process. In this case, the high temperature enables for quick rearrangement of Rh-PCBs into a new coordination crosslink topology, which is then reinforced by their slow mobility upon cooling, so that Rh-PCB aggregates can withstand forces exerted by the deformed polymer network. The obtained shape is preserved after the external load is removed (Figure 6a). The shape-forming process was realized by heating the specimen to 80 °C for 20 min and deforming it into the desired shape. The new shape was then fixed by keeping the deformed sample at 80 °C for 1 h and cooling it to room temperature for another hour while maintaining the load. This technique was demonstrated by producing variously shaped forms from a ribbon of Rh-PCPN-(7) (Figure 6b).

The role of temperature on the shape-forming process and the degree of shape fixation was investigated with stress-relaxation experiments (Figure 6c). Rh-PCPN-(7) samples were stretched to 100% strain at different temperatures (25, 50, and 80 °C) and residual stress was then measured as a function of time. After loading, the internal remnant stress relaxes to a minimum value, σ_{\min} , measured at $t = 60$ min.

We observe remnant stress at all three temperature levels (Figure 6c), but it is noticeably higher at 25 °C, as well as is the initial stress $\sigma_0 = \sigma(t = 0 \text{ min})$ measured immediately after loading. At 25 °C (gray curve), the recorded stress drops from its initial value at $\sigma_0 \approx 4.45$ MPa and relaxes to $\sigma_{\min} = 0.44$ MPa. The stress drop is reduced at 50 °C (blue curve), relaxing from $\sigma_0 \approx 0.55$ MPa to $\sigma_{\min} = 0.19$ MPa, whereas at 80 °C (orange curve), there is only a slight change in stress from $\sigma_0 \approx 0.24$ MPa to $\sigma_{\min} = 0.11$ MPa. This indicates a much stronger interaction between Rh-PCBs at low temperatures. Low σ_{\min} values for 80 and 50 °C suggest much better shape fixation than that at 25 °C. As already pointed out, higher temperatures promote faster ligand exchange interactions that lead to rapid Rh-PCBs

rearrangement after deformation. The ensuing Rh-PCBs re-aggregation upon cooling was confirmed with 2D-SAXS experiments (Figure 6d), where a noticeable shift in diffraction peak is seen before and after the deformation is imprinted. Moreover, the clear difference in diffraction peak positions recorded parallel and perpendicular to applied strain shows anisotropic distribution of Rh-PCBs across the specimen.

2.5. Modular Fabrication of Rh-PCPN-Based Specimen with Complex Shape

Rh-PCB aggregates are not affected by elevated temperatures and the dissociation of coordination points occur only when the Rh-PCPN system is perturbed by an applied mechanical load (apart from solvent swelling). However, the ligand exchange rate does increase with temperature and propagates faster diffusion of Rh-PCBs over the specimen. This enables the material with a self-healing capability, since the dynamical coordination points and polymer chains have the ability to migrate through the interface when joined. The two surfaces can be fused together via a newly formed crosslinking configuration that spans over both parts.

Diffusion of Rh-PCBs between two samples has been demonstrated by preparing two covalently crosslinked poly[(*n*-BA)-*co*-DPPST] films with 7 mol% of DPPST (detailed description of synthesis can be found in the Supporting Information), where one was left untreated (cc-P) and another complexed with rhodium ions to form a covalently crosslinked Rh-PCPN (cc-Rh-PCPN). The two films were placed on top of each other, compressed and heated for 6 h (Figure 7a). Such bilayers facilitate diffusion of Rh-PCBs from the rhodium-ion-rich cc-Rh-PCPN specimen to the noncomplexed cc-P. Covalent bonding enables for separation of the treated cc-P layer from the composite. The treated sample was investigated with UV-vis (Figure 7b), where the absorbance at 410 nm is increased, indicating the presence of rhodium ions. The absorbance line further increases when samples are treated at higher temperatures. Rhodium-ion concentrations (Figure 7b, inner graph) were determined by comparing the obtained absorbance line with that of a standard (Figure S11, Supporting Information). The concentration of rhodium ions increases accordingly with temperature and seems to reach a maximum at around $4 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mol} \cdot \text{g}^{-1}$ at 80 °C.

Rh-PCB migration can be exploited for contact assembly of multiple Rh-PCPN pieces. The contact quality of fused Rh-PCPN material has been investigated by a lap-shear test (Figure 8a) performed on two fused Rh-PCPN-(7) samples of 5 mm \times 2 mm contact area size, which were compressed together with 30% compressive strain for different durations (from 6 to 48 h) and at various temperatures (25, 50, and 80 °C). Uniaxial tensile tests were performed at ambient temperature to determine the tensile strength (σ_{TS}) of the contact (Figure 8a). In general, higher σ_{TS} values indicate a better contact quality. We have omitted investigations on Rh-PCPN-(4) due to its low Rh-PCB concentration and the fact that the sample did not show all the functionalities of other samples (such as solvent resistance), while the high concentration of rhodium ions prevented a successful fusion of Rh-PCPN-(11) samples even after 72 h of contact time at 80 °C.

Figure 8. Lap-shear tests were performed on two fused Rh-PCPN-(7) samples to determine the contact strength. a) Stress–strain experiments show a typical Rh-PCPN behavior for all samples. b) Tensile strength, σ_{TS} , was chosen for quantification of the contact quality, which rises accordingly with temperature and contact time. Dashed, red line indicates the tensile strength for a nonfused Rh-PCPN-(7) sample. c) Fusion process of two Rh-PCPNs at contact is given in schematic: polymer chains diffuse over the contact area and a new crosslinked topology is created that spans over both Rh-PCPN pieces, fusing them together. d) This process enables modular fabrication of Rh-PCPNs into more elaborate shapes and geometries.

Tensile test results for Rh-PCPN-(7) samples show poor adhesion at room temperature, along with samples assembled at 50 °C for 6 h. In both cases the fused layers slid and detached from each other during testing instead of breaking, as it is the case for well-established contacts (see Figure S13 and Table S4, Supporting Information). Contacts accordingly strengthen with higher temperature and longer assembly times (Figure 8b); therefore, a good-quality contact can already be achieved at 50 °C after 12 h, displaying a tensile strength of $\sigma_{TS}(t = 12 \text{ h}) \approx 2.8$ MPa. Assembly time, i.e., duration of compression and heating during modular fabrication process, influences σ_{TS} only slightly at 50 °C, but there is a significant change for 80 °C where σ_{TS} rises from $\sigma_{TS}(t = 6 \text{ h}) \approx 2.7$ MPa to $\sigma_{TS}(t = 48 \text{ h}) \approx 4$ MPa. This is almost on par with the tensile strength of the Rh-PCPN-(7) material itself, $\sigma_{TS, Rh-PCPN(7)} = 4.2$ MPa.

The Rh-PCPN material can be fabricated into complex geometries or shapes that might not be achievable by conventional polymer processing techniques and machining (Figure 8d). The recombination capability of Rh-PCB clusters means that the material functions are completely restored after the assembly process.

2.6. Mechanical Anisotropy

During reshaping of Rh-PCPN, the overall polymer chain orientation is aligned in the direction of applied stress and the new molecular orientational distribution is, the same way as is

the specimen's shape, kept preserved after the process is completed. The instilled orientation manifests itself in anisotropic mechanical properties of the system (Table S5, Supporting Information), where the material is less prone to deformation along the polymer chain orientation (Figure 9a). A clear difference in Young's modulus along (E_{\parallel}) and perpendicular (E_{\perp}) to the instilled strain is detected in a shape-formed Rh-PCPN-(7) sample (Figure 9b; Table S6, Supporting Information), where $\Delta E = E_{\parallel} - E_{\perp}$ increases consistently with larger applied reshaping strain, ϵ_{RS} . The level of anisotropy can therefore be controlled by varying the amount of applied strain during the reshaping process and since the mechanical anisotropy stays preserved, it can be utilized for directional tuning of mechanical parameters.

Another approach of controlling the amount of mechanical anisotropy is by fusing together reshaped Rh-PCBs in different directions according to the polymer chain orientation (Figure 9a). A 150% strained piece of Rh-PCPN-(7), termed V150, was fused with progressively strained and perpendicularly oriented layer of the same material (termed Hx, where x corresponds to percent of strain) to produce a bilayer composite (V150-Hx). Stress–strain results, performed vertically and horizontally along the composite's surface, show the level of mechanical anisotropy decreasing with less mismatching strains between the two layers (Figure 9c). When two equally strained layers are fused together (V150-H150), the stress–strain curves almost overlap. This is also reflected by the derived Young's modulus difference (Figure 9b), where ΔE approaches zero when the strains of each layer match.

Figure 9. a) Individual Rh-PCPN-(7) pieces were reshaped by applying various reshaping strains, ϵ_{rs} , resulting in anisotropic Young's modulus, ΔE . Reshaped Rh-PCPN-(7) layers were fused together at a 90° angle between each layer's polymer chain orientations. The fusing process was performed at 80°C for 48 h, under 30% compressive strain. A sample was then cut from the center of the fused bilayer for stress-strain experiments. b) The amount of anisotropy in Young's modulus was determined for single layers of reshaped Rh-PCPN-(7) samples (blue bars) and for ensuing bilayer composites (violet bars). Graph (c) depicts stress-strain curves of bilayer composites performed in two directions (vertical, solid line; horizontal, dashed line). The difference in mechanical response is highlighted with color and serves only for visualization purposes.

These two approaches demonstrate options to modify mechanical properties of Rh-PCPNs where directed stress distribution could be achieved by modulating Young's modulus across the material for enhancing structural stability or for providing nonconventional deformations.

3. Conclusion

Rh-PCPN is introduced as a multifunctional soft material relying on the dynamic nature of rhodium-phosphine coordination sites. These Rh-PCBs act as crosslinkers that aggregate into Rh-PCB clusters, providing for additional material stability and enabling the material with aggregation induced emission. Rh-PCB clusters can be dissociated by means of chemical interactions or mechanical strains, giving the material an ability to perform as a sensor device, as the fluorescent emission changes are already triggered by exposure to low solvent concentrations and mechanical friction. Rh-PCPNs are pliable at high temperatures and can be reshaped into intricate geometries due to the fast dynamics of Rh-PCBs. The diffusivity of coordination sites can occur between two Rh-PCPN surfaces, facilitating self-healing. These are exploited for fabrication of objects with complex geometrical designs. The fact that sensing capabilities are not degrading after reshaping or assembly turns the Rh-PCPN materials into candidates for sensor devices, especially

when complex geometries are required. Reshaping also introduces anisotropy to elastic properties of the specimen. The structure function of the fabricated specimen can be customized through assembly of differently reshaped Rh-PCPN pieces, e.g., enabling redistribution of mechanical stresses. Rh-PCPN materials might be of relevance for soft robotic technologies, which relies on active soft materials that can provide sensing capabilities together with elasticity, shape adaptability, and good mechanical and/or chemical durability.

4. Experimental Section

Synthesis of Rh-PCPN-(x): Complexation of the P-(x) (see Supporting Information) with $[\text{RhCl}(\text{COD})]_2$ in a rhodium-to-phosphorous molar stoichiometry of 1:4 created the Rh-PCPN-(x). Here, the synthesis of Rh-PCPN-(7) is described exemplarily: 0.12 mL of $[\text{RhCl}(\text{COD})]_2$ (0.012 g , $2.6 \times 10^{-5}\text{ mol}$) solution in CHCl_3 was added to a solution of poly[(*n*-BA)-*co*-DPPST] (0.4 g , $6.8 \times 10^{-6}\text{ mol}$) in CHCl_3 (4 mL), the mixture was stirred for 10 min, and then transferred into a polytetrafluorethylene petri dish (the casted film could be easily separated from the polytetrafluorethylene petri dish). The cast film was obtained by placing a glass cover over the Teflon at petri dish and allowing the CHCl_3 to evaporate under ambient conditions in a well-ventilated hood for 72 h. The resulting film was extracted with ethanol for 2 h to remove the free COD ligands and afterwards dried in a vacuum oven at 25°C for 48 h to remove residual solvents. Finally, Rh-PCPN-(7) was obtained as a dark yellow-colored film. The Rh-PCPN-(4) and Rh-PCPN-(11) were prepared by the same method.

The mass of $[\text{RhCl}(\text{COD})]_2$ was calculated according to Equation (1). $M_{\text{Rh salt}}$ is the molecular weight of $[\text{RhCl}(\text{COD})]_2$, m_p is the mass of poly[(*n*-BA)-*co*-DPPST], $M_{n\text{-BA}}$ is the molecular weight of *n*-BA, and M_{DPPST} is the molecular weight of DPPST. DC is the molar concentration of DPPST in poly[(*n*-BA)-*co*-DPPST], BC is the molar concentration of *n*-BA in poly[(*n*-BA)-*co*-DPPST], and the constant 8 in the equation results from the Rh/phosphorous molar stoichiometry (1:4) and the molecular structure of metal salts

$$m_{\text{Rh salt}} = \frac{M_{\text{Rh salt}} \times \text{DC} \times m_p}{8 \times (\text{DC} \times M_{\text{DPPST}} + \text{BC} \times M_{n\text{-BA}})} \quad (1)$$

Dissolution Experiments: The dissolution experiments were performed by immersing the Rh-PCPN-(*x*) samples into CHCl_3 , toluene, tetrahydrofuran (THF), and DMF. The degree of swelling (Q) was calculated according to Equation (2), in which m_d is the mass of the dry sample, m_{sw} is the mass of sample swollen in solvent, ρ_1 is the specific density of the swelling media, and ρ_2 is the specific density of the dry sample. The crosslink density (ν_c) was calculated according to Flory–Rehner equation (Equation (3)), in which the ϕ_2 is the volume fraction of the swollen polymer sample, χ_{12} is the Flory solvent–polymer interaction parameter, and V_1 is the molar volume of the swelling media^[35]

$$Q = 1 + \rho_2 \times \left(\frac{m_{\text{sw}}}{m_d \times \rho_1} - \frac{1}{\rho_1} \right) \quad (2)$$

$$\nu_c = \frac{\ln(1 - \phi_2) + \phi_2 + \phi_2^2 \cdot \chi_{12}}{V_1 \left[\left(\frac{\phi_2}{2} \right) - \phi_2^{1/3} \right]} \quad (3)$$

Lap-Shear Tests: In the lap-shear tests, two pieces of Rh-PCPN-(*x*) were laid on top of each other on an area of 5 mm × 2 mm with a compression of 30% for varying time periods (6, 12, 24, and 48 h) and different temperatures (RT, 50, and 80 °C). Afterwards, uniaxial tensile tests were performed with the obtained Rh-PCPN-(*x*) assemblies under a deformation rate of 10 mm min⁻¹ at ambient temperature.

Reshaping Experiment: In the reshaping experiment, the Rh-PCPN-(*x*) sample was heated to 80 °C for 20 min and deformed to the intended shape under application of an external force. Afterwards, the deformed Rh-PCPN-(*x*) sample was kept at 80 °C for 60 min and then cooled at ambient temperature for another 60 min while application of the external force was maintained. Finally, the reshaped Rh-PCPN-(*x*) was obtained after removal of the external force.

General Description of Errors Analysis: Data are reported as mean value ± standard deviation. All standard deviations were obtained by repeating each test for three times.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Keywords

assembly capabilities, fluorescence stimuli-responsivity, multiple functions, reshaping abilities, rhodium(I)–phosphine coordination bonds, solvent resistance

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